

**THE ASPECTS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE
COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO KARAKALPAK GROUPS OF
ACADEMIC LYCEUMS**

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Abstract: *This article explores effective strategies for enhancing the communicative competence of Karakalpak students learning English at academic lyceums. This study investigates the key components of communicative competence—grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic—and their relevance in language acquisition. It further identifies obstacles specific to Karakalpak students, such as linguistic differences, limited real-life communication opportunities, and the prevalence of language anxiety. Through a review of contemporary pedagogical methods, the article suggests practical solutions, including task-based language teaching, interactive activities, and the use of digital tools to create a more immersive learning experience. Additionally, the role of teachers in fostering a supportive, communication-focused environment and providing constructive feedback is emphasized.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, English language teaching, Karakalpak students, academic lyceums, task-based language teaching (TBLT), language learning challenges, multilingual education.*

In today's globalized world, English language proficiency has become essential for students aiming to access broader academic, professional, and cultural opportunities. This need is particularly significant for students in multilingual and multicultural regions such as Karakalpakstan, where learning English can expand prospects and improve cross-cultural communication. However, despite its importance, developing communicative competence—a key aspect of language proficiency that involves the effective and context-appropriate use of language—remains a challenge for many Karakalpak students at academic lyceums. Communicative competence goes beyond mere grammatical knowledge, encompassing the ability to engage in real-life conversations, understand cultural nuances, and use language fluently across various social contexts. For Karakalpak students, achieving communicative competence in English can be difficult due to linguistic and structural differences between Karakalpak and English, limited exposure to English-speaking environments, and a lack of confidence that often hinders spontaneous communication. These factors are compounded by the traditional educational practices that prioritize written skills over spoken communication, limiting students' ability to use English dynamically [5, 39-54].

Developing communicative competence in English poses unique challenges for Karakalpak students, particularly in the context of academic lyceums where English instruction is often limited to formal classroom settings.

One of the primary challenges is the significant linguistic difference between English and the Karakalpak language. English and Karakalpak belong to different language families, with English classified as a Germanic language and Karakalpak as a Turkic language. These languages differ in grammar, syntax, and phonology, making it difficult for students to understand and produce English sentences fluently. For instance, English's complex verb tenses, word order, and use of articles can be unfamiliar and challenging for Karakalpak learners, who may struggle to apply these structures correctly.

Language is deeply rooted in culture, and English communication often involves idiomatic expressions, social norms, and references that may not exist in Karakalpak culture. Karakalpak students may find it challenging to interpret cultural nuances in English conversations, potentially leading to misunderstandings or hesitation in engaging with English speakers. Additionally, the more reserved communication style in Karakalpak society may contribute to difficulties in adapting to the relatively direct and interactive style often expected in English-speaking contexts.

Many Karakalpak students experience language anxiety, which can significantly impact their willingness to communicate in English. Fear of making mistakes or being judged by peers can inhibit students from participating actively in class or attempting conversations outside the classroom. This anxiety often leads to a reluctance to practice spoken English, limiting the development of their communicative competence. Low self-confidence and self-efficacy in using English further exacerbate this issue, as students may feel less capable of improving their skills. Outside the classroom, Karakalpak students have limited exposure to English, as English-language media, environments, and social opportunities are scarce. Unlike learners in regions with more English-speaking communities or media presence, Karakalpak students may not have access to immersive experiences that reinforce language learning. This lack of exposure limits their ability to practice English in real-world settings, reducing opportunities for organic vocabulary acquisition, listening skills, and cultural understanding [6, 180-194].

The traditional educational approach in many academic lyceums focuses heavily on grammar, reading, and writing skills rather than spoken and interactive language use. This focus often results in students excelling in written tests but struggling with conversational skills. Additionally, large class sizes and limited teaching resources

make it challenging for educators to offer personalized attention or create interactive language-learning environments. The emphasis on written examinations may discourage students from developing the confidence and fluency needed for effective communication. While many English teachers in Karakalpakstan are dedicated, they may lack access to specialized training in communicative teaching methods or resources that facilitate active language use. Without training in methods such as task-based language teaching or communicative language teaching, teachers may resort to traditional lecture-based approaches. Limited access to materials like audio-visual aids, language labs, or online resources also restricts teachers' ability to create an engaging, interactive classroom that fosters communicative competence.

Addressing the challenges faced by Karakalpak students in developing communicative competence requires adopting targeted strategies that foster both practical language use and confidence in real-life communication.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) focuses on engaging students in real-life tasks that require meaningful language use, promoting active communication and collaboration. In TBLT, students participate in activities such as role-playing scenarios, planning trips, or solving problems, all of which require them to use English to achieve specific outcomes. By focusing on completing a task rather than just learning language rules, TBLT helps students develop fluency, gain confidence, and practice conversational skills in contexts that resemble real-life situations. Interactive classroom activities, such as group discussions, debates, and role-plays, encourage students to use English dynamically, helping them gain experience in both speaking and listening. These activities foster a sense of collaboration, reduce anxiety by creating a supportive environment, and allow students to experiment with language in a low-pressure setting. For example, students might engage in group discussions on familiar topics or role-play common scenarios, such as ordering food at a restaurant or describing a cultural event, giving them opportunities to practice and improve their communicative competence. Incorporating technology in language learning can be particularly effective for Karakalpak students, who have limited exposure to English outside the classroom.

Language learning apps, online conversation partners, and multimedia resources (such as podcasts, videos, and language games) can provide students with additional practice and immersion. Technology also allows for virtual exchanges with English speakers, creating opportunities for authentic communication that would otherwise be inaccessible. Additionally, video-based resources can introduce students to various accents, vocabulary, and cultural contexts, enriching their overall language

experience. Creating a supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable making mistakes is essential for building communicative competence. Teachers can foster this environment by encouraging risk-taking in language use, showing patience, and giving positive reinforcement. Small-group work, peer support, and activities that build trust among students can also reduce anxiety and help students feel more confident in using English. When students feel safe to express themselves, they are more likely to participate actively and take advantage of opportunities to improve their communication skills [4].

Using authentic materials, such as news articles, advertisements, and dialogues from real conversations, can help students engage with English in a more meaningful way. Authentic materials expose students to natural language use, providing examples of how English is spoken in everyday contexts. By practicing with these materials, students become more familiar with colloquial expressions, idioms, and cultural references, all of which enhance their ability to understand and participate in real-world English conversations.

Feedback plays a crucial role in language development, but it needs to be constructive to avoid discouraging students. Teachers can use correction techniques that focus on fluency before accuracy, allowing students to express their ideas freely without fear of immediate criticism. Delayed feedback—providing corrections after a task is completed—can help students focus on communication during activities. Positive reinforcement, such as acknowledging improvements or highlighting successful communication efforts, can also boost students' motivation and confidence in their abilities. Traditional written exams may not adequately assess students' communicative competence. Instead, alternative assessment methods, such as oral exams, peer reviews, and self-assessments, can provide a more accurate measure of students' speaking and listening skills. For instance, teachers can conduct regular oral proficiency tests where students engage in conversations on various topics, allowing them to demonstrate their ability to use language effectively. Peer and self-assessments also encourage students to reflect on their progress, which promotes self-awareness and continuous improvement.

Conclusion. Improving communicative competence in English among Karakalpak students at academic lyceums is crucial for equipping them with the language skills needed for academic success, professional development, and broader cross-cultural interactions. This article has explored the unique challenges that these students face, from linguistic and cultural barriers to limited exposure and traditional teaching practices that often prioritize written skills over spoken interaction. By

addressing these obstacles with targeted strategies and innovative teaching methods, educators can significantly enhance students' ability to communicate effectively in English. Task-based language teaching, interactive classroom activities, and the use of technology create engaging opportunities for students to practice English in meaningful contexts, promoting both fluency and confidence. The role of teachers in fostering a supportive and inclusive environment is equally essential, as it encourages students to overcome language anxiety and take risks in their language use.

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